

PROCESSING OF CARBON/CARBON COMPOSITES BASED UPON CHEMICAL VAPOR INFILTRATION AND POLYMER PYROLYSIS METHODS

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ABSTRACT

Carbon/carbon composites fabricated by both the chemical vapor infiltration (CVI) route as well as liquid resin impregnation method are examined. In the CVI process, a mixture of methane and argon is channeled into the reactor at one atmosphere. The deposition of pyrolytic carbon within a fibrous preform at various temperature and deposition period is examined. The vapor infiltration depth and matrix deposition gradient within the carbon preform are also investigated. For carbon/carbon composites fabricated by the polymer pyrolysis method, phenolic resins are vacuum-impregnated into the carbon fibrous preform, and the graphite/phenolic composites are cured at 160°C, followed by a postcuring process at the temperature range of 100 to 250°C. The studies include the measurements of weight gain, bulk density, flexural strength and flexural modulus of the carbon/carbon composites prepared by these two methods, and the examination of microstructures of specimens fabricated by these two processes are also made.

Keywords: Carbon/carbon composites, chemical vapor infiltration, polymer pyrolysis

1. INTRODUCTION

The fabrication of carbon/carbon (C/C) composites through deposition of Pyro C via pyrolytic hydrocarbon gas within fibrous preforms at elevated temperature is a well developed technique^[1-4]. The process involves the infiltration of hydrocarbon gas from preform surface to the interior of the preform, adsorption of the gas on the fiber surface, chemical reactions and deposition of product(s) onto the fiber surface, desorption from fiber surface, and diffusion of the gas phase product(s) from interior of the preform to the preform surface^[5,6]. The performance of the C/C composite is affected by the microstructure of the deposited matrix which is significantly influenced by the experimental conditions. The conditions include deposition temperature, pressure, gas composition, gas flow rate, and properties of deposition substrate^[4-5,7]. In this study, weight gain and density of the specimens fabricated under various deposition periods and experimental conditions are measured. Tests on flexural strength and flexural modulus of the specimens are also made.

On the liquid impregnation method, the combination of liquid resin and carbon fibers can serve as the starting materials for carbon/carbon composites. The process is accomplished by pyrolysis of the liquid resin and carbonization treatment of residual carbon. The precursor for the liquid impregnation process should have a high carbon yield, which implies a low weight loss during carbonization. The mass loss results in bulk shrinkage which leads to the formation of a porous carbon composite. Densification is achieved by multiple impregnation with carbon precursor and subsequent recarbonization. The fabrication parameters for carbonization depend on the matrix precursor used. For example, coal tar pitch results in a high carbon yield when carbonization process is executed in a very slow manner or under high pressure; on the other hand, thermoset

resins do not need pressure carbonization^[5]. The mechanical properties of carbon/carbon composites are influenced by the matrix microstructure, fiber/matrix interface, and the high temperature treatment between the impregnation and carbonization cycles^[8,9]. Porous carbon/carbon composite forms as a result of volatile generation and mass loss of solid materials during polymer pyrolysis. Part of the decomposed gases are trapped, resulting in pressure gradient within the composite. The generation of pressure gradient within a matrix may cause cracks and voids to form^[10].

The objective of this study is to examine the weight gain and density variation of C/C composites fabricated by both the chemical vapor infiltration technique and liquid impregnation method under different processing conditions. The flexural strength and flexural modulus of the composites are measured to investigate the relationship among density, mechanical properties, and processing conditions. X-ray diffraction is utilized to investigate the structural rearrangement in the carbonized composite. The deposition gradient of the matrix by pyrolysis of the hydrocarbon gas is also examined by optical microscopy.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

Materials and specimen processing

The fiber material used in this study is in the form of 2-D carbon fabrics, which are impregnated with phenolic resin using a wet dipping technique and then placed in an air circulation oven at 70°C for 2 hours to remove excess solvent. The impregnated fabrics are then placed in a picture frame mold and compression molded at 160°C under 2500 psi pressure. The resulting polymer composites are postcured in an air circulation oven at 150°C for 36 hours. The volume fraction of fiber in the polymer composite is near 75 %. The test specimens are cut to 50x10x1 mm by a diamond tip saw under water cooling. The initial carbonization treatment is carried out in a high temperature tube furnace to 1200°C under Ar atmosphere.

Densification of composites by chemical vapor infiltration

The densification by isothermal chemical vapor infiltration is performed in a horizontal tube furnace. Methane is used as a source of carbon, and argon is used as a carrier gas. The volume fraction of methane is 25 %. Total gas flow rate is 150 cm³/min. The methane gas is channeled into the reactor after the temperature in furnace dwelled at the processing temperature for 30 minutes.

Densification of composites by liquid impregnation

Phenolic resin is adopted as the precursor in liquid impregnation technique under vacuum to densify the C/C composites. The phenolic resin is diluted to 80-100 cps by acetone. The un-densified C/C composites are then immersed in the dilute resin under vacuum until the weight of composites ceases to change. After impregnation, the composites are cured in an air circulation oven at 160°C and postcured in the same oven for 36 hours at 150°C. The specimens are then placed in a high temperature tube furnace and heated to 1000°C under Ar atmosphere for carbonization. The re-impregnation is repeated several times.

Density measurement

The density of composites are measured on a Precica 180A microbalance using water immerse method.

Weight gain measurement

Weight gain of the composites is determined by the difference in weight between densified and un-densified C/C composites. The weight of composites is measured on a Precia 180A microbalance to ± 0.0001 g.

Flexure properties measurement

Flexural properties are measured by a three point bending test with span to depth ratio of 40 and crosshead speed is 1.3 mm/min. All tests are performed on an Instron testing machine model 4201. All tests follow the ASTM D-790 specification.

Microstructure examination

X-ray diffraction was utilized to investigate the structure rearrangement in the carbonized composites after treated under different temperatures. All specimens are analyzed by copper radiation, using a computer controlled power diffractometer, at a speed of 4°/min at 40 KV and 30 mA.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows the weight gain and density increase for composite fabricated by chemical vapor infiltration. Curve A and curve B represent the weight gain and density increment, respectively, of the composites fabricated by CVI for various periods of infiltration. For specimens fabricated at 1200°C, a severe deposition gradient is observed; a thick layer of deposition on the composite surface is measured, whereas nearly no deposition in the interior is detected. This is probably the reason why the density variation in Curve B becomes flat as the processing temperature is increased.

Figure 2 shows the weight gain and density variation for composites prepared by CVI at 1000°C for various processing periods. It is found that the longer the processing periods, the higher the weight gain and density increase.

Figure 3 shows the weight gain and density increase for composites fabricated by liquid impregnation. As the impregnation process proceeds, the increments in both the mass and density become smaller. It is understandable because the pore size and number become smaller as impregnation proceeds; the impregnation depth is reduced if the applied pressure (near 1 atm in this work) is kept unchanged during impregnation.

The pore development during fabrication in CVI may differ from that fabricated through liquid impregnation. In liquid impregnation route, the pores form due to shrinkage of the polymer filling the voids. On the other hand, for composites fabricated by CVI, the pore size reduces gradually due to the constant deposition of the product(s) on the pore surface.

Comparing the density variation of the composites fabricated by resin impregnation and CVI, the difference in matrix density increment rate (density increment/total processing time) of these two methods is obvious. The density increases from 1.420 to 1.561 (g/cm³) for composites fabricated for 48 hrs at 1000°C. On the other hand, the density increase from 1.420 to 1.516 (g/cm³) after three times of impregnation. The processing period for each impregnation is 56 hrs.

Curves A, B, and C in Figure 4 represent the relationship between flexural strength and weight gain under conditions A, B, and C, respectively. It is found that the higher the weight gain, the higher the flexural strength will be. Among these three fabrication conditions, the increase in flexural strength for the composites fabricated by CVI at 1000°C for various processing periods is most obvious. Figure 5 shows the relationship between flexural modulus and weight gain under the same conditions listed in Figure 4. Curve A in Figure 5 shows that a higher flexural modulus is obtained if polymer impregnation method is applied.

Figure 6 shows the interlayer spacing and diffraction peak of Bragg angles for composites fabricated at various processing temperatures for 12 hours. It is obvious that a more perfect structure can be obtained when a higher processing temperature is applied.

Figure 7 shows the gradient of deposition thickness within composites. The data are normalized by assuming that the deposition thickness at the outer surface of the C/C composites is one. The

deposition thickness is measured from Optical Microscopy (OM) pictures. Once a higher processing temperature is adopted, the deposition gradient becomes severe due to a higher reaction rate at higher temperature. Therefore a significant species concentration depletion occurs during vapor infiltration; similar results were observed in Ref. [11] which theoretically investigated the deposition profile under various processing conditions for fabricating ceramic matrix composites by CVI.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The fabrication of carbon/carbon composites by both CVI as well as liquid impregnation are performed. A higher flexural strength and flexural modulus can be obtained as the density of the specimens are increased by the deposition of carbon or by the pyrolysis of the matrix precursor. The interlayer spacing of the C/C composites is reduced as the temperature for CVI is increased. The deposition gradient of Pyro C within the carbon preform becomes severe when the deposition temperature is increased.

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Figure 1. The weight gain and density of C/C composites densified by CVI at various deposition temperatures for 12 hours.

Figure 2. The weight gain and density of C/C composites densified by CVI at 1000°C for various processing time.

Figure 3. The weight gain and density of C/C composites densified by resin re-impregnation process at various re-impregnation times.

Figure 4. Flexural strength v.s. weight gain of C/C composites densified by the following conditions: (A) Resin re-impregnation process, (B) CVI process at various temperatures for 12 hours, and (C) CVI process at 1000°C for various processing times.

Figure 5. Flexural modulus v.s. weight gain of C/C composites densified by the following conditions: (A) Resin re-impregnation process, (B) CVI process at various temperature for 12 hours, and (C) CVI process at 1000°C for various processing time.

Figure 6. The X-Ray Diffraction 2θ and interlayer spacing of C/C composites densified by the CVI process at various processing temperature for 12 hours.

Figure 7. Deposition gradient within composites fabricated by the CVI process under various processing temperatures.